

D3.1 Provision of first combined information

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Markus Donat (BSC), Carlos Delgado-Torres (BSC), Pep Cos (BSC), David Sexton (MO), Muhammad Adnan Abid (UOXF), Beena Balan Sarojini (UOXF), Antje Weisheimer (UOXF)

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* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

** **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Executive Summary

Providing seamless climate predictions by combining the information from different forecasts or different forecast systems is one of the central goals of the ASPECT project. Different methods are being developed to achieve this, typically applied as a post-processing to existing climate simulations. This deliverable provides the first combined information from these different 'temporal merging' techniques. As these techniques make use of existing climate simulations, we aim to define approaches of sharing the relevant information that avoid duplication of data already available in public archives. We therefore propose to provide this combined information through files that allow users to identify the climate simulation data to be used for a specific prediction at a specific start date. We propose YAML files as a suitable file format to provide this information, which are intuitive, machine and human readable and flexible to accommodate specific needs of different methods. For approaches that have been published already, these files are available at Zenodo and documented in this report, whereas for other approaches still in development the possible format for future data provision is outlined in the report. Within ASPECT, these files provide the necessary information to construct user-relevant seamless predictions that can be used by WP4 and WP6 to develop seamless near-term climate information targeted to specific user needs.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To incorporate a diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing methods enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Introduction

A key focus of ASPECT is on bridging traditional prediction and projection time scales for the provision of seamless climate prediction information. Besides producing new initialised predictions that bridge the seasonal-to-multiannual and decadal-to-multidecadal timescales (which is done in ASPECT WP1), the research in ASPECT WP3 (Task 3.3) aims to develop methods that combine or merge the information from different existing climate predictions and projections, with the goal of making prediction information more useful to society, as users across many sectors are typically interested in making decisions across several timescales. These existing simulations typically provide global seasonal or decadal climate predictions, or century-long climate projections. Different methods are being developed that combine (or 'merge') information from these different climate simulations, towards providing seamless climate information for the near-term and more distant future (from seasons to multiple decades into the future).

This deliverable presents first solutions to share the climate information from merging predictions and projections traditionally targeting different time scales. It is envisaged that

these methods could be used for climate services for a range of potential users, and depending on the method, they could be further developed to explore applicability to other hazards linked to large scale drivers, or particular regions of interest. Some of these initial data reflect initial methodological development tailored toward specific Super User focussed needs, with the user engagement and climate service prototype development occurring in WP4 (user engagement information available in Deliverable 4.1). This deliverable is a data release rather than a comprehensive guide to the methods as they are broadly still under development and not yet published, but for context we explain briefly the purpose of the data and why it is useful.

2 Considerations for sharing climate information combined from different predictions

These methods build on existing data, which are typically available in publicly accessible data archives. For instance, the seasonal predictions can be accessed through the Climate Data Store (CDS; <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>) of the Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S), which provides guidelines on how to download the datasets manually on the web or programmatically using an API service. On the other hand, the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF; <https://esgf.llnl.gov/>) provide access to the simulations performed within the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6; Eyring et al. 2016), including decadal hindcasts and predictions, historical forcing simulations, and climate projection scenarios, also providing manual and code-based options to download the data.

In addition, some methods also make use of novel prediction datasets developed and produced within ASPECT, such as the new multi-annual predictions conducted under WP1. At present these novel prediction products are not yet available in the public domain, but as the project develops these simulations could be made publicly available. Specifically, these multi-annual simulations combined with the seasonal forecast are used to develop the seamless climate information for the tailored extremes on seasonal to multi-annual time scales (see Section 3.2). Currently, for ECMWF the multi-annual simulations can be retrieved from the MARS server as information mentioned in WP6.

Therefore, for sharing information of the combined/temporally merged predictions it does not seem efficient or necessary to duplicate data that is already widely available for download elsewhere. Instead, we prefer to provide information that clearly identifies those specific simulations (e.g. model name, ensemble, member, initialisation date) that are selected by a specific method for specific starting dates. We identified YAML files as a suitable format to provide this information. YAML is a human-readable (and machine-readable) data serialization language. It is an easy, intuitive and flexible data format, and often used for configuration files but also for data exchange. While each method has its specific characteristics or needs of how the information is most suitably shared with potential users, the structure and content of the YAML files can be adjusted to cater these needs. Within the ASPECT project, Work Packages WP4 and WP6 provide the user engagement and climate service prototype design with technical expertise, data storage and sharing, thus providing an interface to engage with the sectorial users who might themselves not have sufficient technical expertise to read and process climate model data.

3 Documentation of data formats for the sharing of ‘temporal merging’ data

Different approaches to merge climate information from different predictions are being developed within ASPECT. These methods typically select subsets from large ensembles of climate simulations, or combine specific simulations from specific start dates or simulation members.

In the following we describe the specific design of the files for sharing temporally combined climate information for each of the different methods. This deliverable is designed only for data provision for methods developed so far, and associated detail needed to interpret and further use the data, and is not intended to provide full details of the methodology. Note that much of this work is still subject to ongoing research activities and thus under development.

3.1 Selecting sub-sets of decadal climate predictions and long-term climate projections (BSC)

The analogue-based selection methods were first developed by Mahmood et al. (2021) and Mahmood et al. (2022), and further developed and tested within ASPECT by De Luca et al. (2023), Cos et al. (2024) and Donat et al. (2024). They identify in each year those simulations from a large ensemble of transient historical and scenario runs that are in closest agreement with the climate state based on observations or initialised decadal predictions. The level of agreement is typically identified from global or regional sea surface temperature anomaly patterns, e.g. via spatial correlations (for details please refer to the references quoted above). Ongoing work also transfers the method to merge information from seasonal and decadal predictions, selecting decadal predictions based on their agreement with seasonal predictions initialised at different times.

The YAML files therefore need to provide unambiguous identifiers of the specific simulations chosen at each start date. Such identifier can typically be constructed from a combination of the model name and the identifiers of specific ensemble members (e.g. *r1i1f1p1*, *r2i1f1p1*, etc.) as used within the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6). The studies performed within ASPECT applied different methodologies and had different quantities of data available. As part of this deliverable we provide the data associated with two recent publications: Cos et al. (2024) and Donat et al. (2024). These data are available at the following Zenodo repository links:

- Cos et al. (2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14393191>
- Donat et al. (2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14393338>

Each YAML file first provides a brief description of the methodological details in the header (such as the accumulation period, constraint region and variable, original ensemble size, and constraining approach, along with references to the scientific articles where it was used), which is then followed by a list of ranked members for each initialisation date (formatted as `[model]_[run_identifier]`; note that specific version numbers of published CMIP6 experiments are not currently part of the information provided but could potentially be included if requested). The initialisation dates are indicated by “s1961:”, “s1962:”, etc., after which the different ensemble members are then listed in descending order according to their similarity; i.e. those members most similar to the observed or decadal predictions-based climate states (measured

e.g. through spatial correlations) are listed first. The users can then select the first N members according to their requirements. Most previous studies have used the top-ranked $N=30$ ensemble members, different numbers can be chosen depending on application.

The ranking of members per start date is stored in YAML files available on Zenodo (see links provided above). These files provide a standardised format for recording and sharing rankings of members, ensuring transparency and reproducibility. For instance, the file *RankedMembers_accumyears9_constraintregionGlobal_ensemble209.yaml* has the following structure:

- Description:
 - Accumulation years: 9.0
 - Constraint region: Global
 - Constraint variable: SST
 - Ensemble size: 209.0
 - Constraint approach: Climate projections constrained by observations (Mahmood et al. 2022; Cos et al. 2024)
- s1961:
 - GISS-E2-1-G_r10i1p1f2
 - EC-Earth3_r12i1p1f1
 - CanESM5_r21i1p2f1
 - ...
- s1962:
 - ...
- ...
- s2000:
 - ...

Where in the header, “*Accumulation years*” indicates that the constraint has been applied based on 9-year averages, using global (*Constraint region*) SST (*Constraint variable*) anomalies, and applying the constraint to a total *Ensemble size* of 209 climate projections. For the initialisations in 1961 (*s1961:*), the highest ranked ensemble member is GISS-E2-1-G_r10i1p1f2 (meaning: the run with identifier r10i1p1f2 of the model GISS-E2-1-G), the second-highest ranked member is EC-Earth3_r12i1p1f1, etc. A similar list of ranked members is then included below for the other start years (s1962, s1963, etc.).

Additionally, some example code in R and Python to read these files is provided both in the data documentation on Zenodo and in the box below:

EXAMPLE CODE SNIPPETS FOR READING FILES

```
###--- R ---###
# install.packages("yaml") # Install YAML package if not already
# installed
library(yaml) # Load the YAML package
file <-
'RankedMembers_accumyears9_constraintregionGlobal_ensemble209.yaml'
member_list <- yaml.load_file(file) # Load the YAML file
```

```

print(member_list[['s1970']][1:30]) # Print the top 30 members for
the start date 1970

###--- Python ---###
# pip install pyyaml # Install YAML package if not already
installed
import yaml # Load the YAML package
file =
'RankedMembers_accumyears9_constraintregionGlobal_ensemble209.yaml'
with open(file, "r") as f: # Load the YAML file
    member_list = yaml.safe_load(f)
print(member_list['s1970'][0:30]) # Print the top 30 members for
the start date 1970

```

3.2 Combining initialised predictions from different initialisation times (UOXF)

The development of the temporal merging methodology on seasonal to multi-annual time scales is one of the key developments in the ASPECT project. The idea of this is to inform the users about any climate information they are interested in on seasonal to multi-annual timescales. Most recently, the new extended multi-annual forecast simulations are conducted by the modeling centres involved in WP1. These simulations along with the standard seasonal forecasts are used to develop the seamless climate information on seasonal to multi-annual timescale. The methodology used to develop the seamless information from season to multi-annual timescales is named as “*Pooling ensemble*” as shown in eq. (1),

$$Pooling\ Ensemble = \sum_{i=1}^k W_i F_i(m, x, y) \quad (1)$$

Here “F” represents the forecast, where “i” is for each start date and “k” the total start dates available, while “W” represents weight and “m” represents the ensemble members.

The above methodology is different from the one used for the merging on decadal to the projections (CMIP6 models) timescales (as outlined e.g. in Section 3.1). In this case, we are using the initialized runs with varying magnitude of skill for the particular events, which we tailor to a specific use case of interest. This methodology will help to develop a stable seamless system by providing large ensemble size. Currently this method is used for the ECMWF forecast available from seasonal to multi-annual timescale. The first case where this methodology is adopted is for the vineyard case in the Catalonia region, where we merged all the forecasts available from year-2 to year-0 to forecast Frequency of the Frost Days (FFD) in the Spring season as per the user requirement (more information is available in Deliverable 4.1). The outcome of this temporal merging is large ensemble size using all the available ensemble members from year-2 to year-0 start dates.

For example, if a user likes to forecast Spring FFD in 2025 using ECMWF multi-annual forecast, one can take a forecast 2 years prior to the event, i.e., Nov 2023, which has a total

25 ensemble members available. Then, the next forecast start date available is for May (May 2024) which has 15 ensemble members, and so on. This information is listed in the file description below. Then using eq. (1), all the forecasts can be stacked together in a single file as the temporally merged information. Please see the example YAML file mentioned below.

As this method is still under development, the data outline provided below is just an illustration of the outcome. The details of this method and the data will be archived through a suitable repository, once the method will be published.

Description of YAML file :

Data_Source: MARS_Server

Variable: MinimumTemperature (T_min)

Derived_variable: Frequency_of_Frost_Days (FFD)

Definition: FFD (T_min < 0 deg)

Model/Forecasting_System: ECMWF_SEAS5

Original_data_format: NetCDF

Reference: Abid_etal_[in_prep]

Region: Global

Target_Forecast_Year: "2025"

Target_Season: March-April

Temporal_Merging_Approach: Pooling_Ensemble_members

Total_Ensemble_members: 257

Year0_2025(Forecast_Start_Dates:Ensemble_size):

MarY0_Start: 25

FebY0_Start: 51

JanY0_Start: 25

Year1_2024(Forecast_Start_Dates:Ensemble_size):

DecY1_Start: 25

NovY1_Start: 51

OctY1_Start: 25

AugY1_Start: 15

MayY1_Start: 15

Year2_2023(Forecast_Start_Dates:Ensemble_size):

NovY2_Start: 25

MayY2_Start_(not_used): 25

3.3 Widening sub-set of climate projections (Met Office)

This approach works in the context that the user currently has long-term information from CMIP6 and wants to understand the added value of initialisation for their hazard of interest. This method is currently being developed under ASPECT. The aim is to identify members of the set of CMIP6 long-term uninitialised simulations that are consistent with the "contribution of initialisation" (Smith et al 2019) for an appropriate index of a large-scale driver that is relevant to the hazard(s) of interest. Examples are ENSO, annual mean global temperature, winter and

summer NAO, and summer sub-polar North Atlantic SSTs. The contribution of initialisation is the decadal prediction once the forced signal (both anthropogenic and due to natural sources such as solar and volcanic eruptions) has been removed using linear regression (Smith et al 2019). Following Befort et al (2020), the ensemble mean of the predicted residual due to initialisation is used to shadow CMIP6 realisations that have suitably close deviations from their own forced signal. The main difference from Befort et al (2020) and the methods outlined in section 3.1, is that rather than pick the N closest realisations, the method uses the uncertainty in the forecast to determine which members should be retained. As a forecast signal varies with lead time, and its uncertainty grows with lead time, the number of CMIP6 members that are retained also varies with lead time. At lead time of one year, T+1, members that are most consistent with the 9-year forecast from T+1 are retained. At lead time of two years, T+2, members that are most consistent with the 8-year forecast from T+2 are retained, as well as members already included at T+1. And so on. Gradually the number of realisations will increase with lead time as the value from the initialisation wanes. Then users can look at their hazard of interest in the lead time-dependent subset relative to the full CMIP6 spread to understand the added value from initialisation.

The output is a list of CMIP6 realisations that varies with start year and lead time. In essence, this is very similar to the output from section 3.1 with (i) the extra dependence on lead time, T+x, and (ii) that not all the CMIP6 members might not be retained by the end of the forecast period. Therefore, we have evolved our metadata from the YAML format of section 3.1 and the python and R snippets will be very similar. *As the method is still in development, the outline below is just illustrative. When the method has been published, YAML files for key large-scale drivers will be uploaded to a suitable repository.*

Description:

```

Accumulation years: 9
Constraint approach: Sexton et al (in prep)
Constraint season: JJA
Constraint variable: SPNA
Ensemble size: 300
Ensemble source: CMIP6
s1963, T+1:
- CESM2-FV2_r1i2p2f1
- CanESM5_r7i1p2f1

- GISS-E2-1-G_r2i1p3f1
- CanESM5_r6i1p1f1
s1963, T+2:
- CESM2-FV2_r1i2p2f1
- CanESM5_r7i1p2f1
- GISS-E2-1-G_r2i1p3f1
- CanESM5_r6i1p1f1
- MIROC6_r40i1p1f1
- MPI-ESM1-2-LR_r42i1p1f1
- MPI-ESM1-2-LR_r39i1p1f1
- CanESM5_r2i1p1f1
- MIROC-ES2H_r3i1p4f2
.
.

```

```
.
s1963, T+9:
- CESM2-FV2_r1i2p2f1
.
.
.
s1963, not used:
- CAMS-CSM1-0_r1i1p1f1
- FGOALS-g3_r1i1p1f1
- FGOALS-g3_r2i1p1f1
- FGOALS-g3_r4i1p1f1
- IITM-ESM_r1i1p1f1
- CanESM5_r1i1p1f1
- CanESM5_r4i1p1f1
s1964, T+1:
.
.
.
etc
```

4 Conclusions

This deliverable presents our first suggested solutions for the provision of combined climate information from the different temporal merging techniques developed within ASPECT. These temporal merging techniques are typically applied as a post-processing to existing climate predictions and projections, which are available in different archives such as ESGF or the C3S Climate Data Store. To avoid duplication of these massive data volumes, we suggest providing the information as lists that allow users of a given method to identify and select the specific climate simulations used for the prediction at a certain time step. We provide this information in machine-readable YAML files, which are intuitive and flexible. The specific format of these files can be easily adjusted to the specific needs of a certain method.

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